

Reduction of Breast Surface Dose, Cancer and Mortality Risks Using Lead Apron during the Head Scanning a Computed Tomography Technique

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Article type: Original Paper</p> <hr/> <p>Article history: Received: Jan 25, 2022 Accepted: Apr 17, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords: Computed Tomography Radiation Protection Head Breast Thermoluminescent Dosimetry</p>	<p>Introduction: The present study aimed to assess the reduction of breast surface dose, breast radiation-induced cancer incidence, and mortality risks when the lead apron shielding was positioned on the chest regions during head computed tomography (CT).</p> <p>Material and Methods: In this study, routine head CT scans were performed on 28 female patients with a mean body mass index (BMI) of 25.2 ± 2.8 kg/m². The common lead aprons (0.5 mm thicknesses) were folded and positioned in the chest regions. The breast surface doses were measured using six thermoluminescent dosimeters (TLD-100), three TLDs were located above the apron and three ones positioned under the apron. Breast radiation-induced cancer incidence and mortality risks were estimated using the Biological Effects of Ionizing Radiation (BEIR-VII) model. Finally, the measured doses and cancer/mortality risks were compared using Paired sample T-Test in SPSS software.</p> <p>Results: The breast surface doses under and over the apron were obtained at 0.18 ± 0.06 and 0.49 ± 0.13 mGy, respectively, (P-value < 0.05). Although all cancer/mortality risks for both groups (over and under the apron) were very low, using the lead apron could decrease (significantly) breast cancer incidence risk ($[1.24 \pm 0.32] \times 10^{-3}$ % over the apron vs. $[0.46 \pm 0.15] \times 10^{-3}$ % under the apron) and mortality risk ($[0.30 \pm 0.08] \times 10^{-3}$ % over the apron vs. $[0.11 \pm 0.04] \times 10^{-3}$ % under the apron) about 63% in all patients.</p> <p>Conclusion: The use of common lead aprons in the chest regions for patients undergoing head CT scans could significantly reduce the breast surface doses and radiation-induced cancer/mortality risks.</p>

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Introduction

Computed tomography (CT) is considered the most convenient diagnostic tool in terms of availability, efficiency, and cost [1,2]. However, it accounts for one of the main ionization radiation sources in medical procedures. In addition, the use of CT scans has been increased due to the higher diagnostic value [3,4]. Notably, the radiation doses to the patients in CT scans are higher than the other tools which generate ionization radiation like radiography [5]; therefore, concerns about radiation side effects related to CT examinations have been raised.

Some of the organs are considered sensitive due to the high tissue-weighting factor (W_T) following International Commission on Radiation Protection (ICRP) reports [5]. For instance, the W_T of the breast is 0.12, which accounts for a sensitive organ. On the other hand, head CT scans are common procedures

and perform in a high number daily to determine the incidence and risk factors, especially after head trauma, to investigate the clinical significance of progressive hemorrhage [6-8]. The breast is one of the organs which undergo scattered and leakage radiation during head examinations; therefore, any simple methods cause to reduce the dose received would be crucial [9].

There are several ways and shielding materials used for breast protection. For example, in a study [10], the breast dose was reduced by 11-31% using split protocols (changing the scanning field location) compared to the standard one. In addition, using a bismuth shield for the breast during chest CT examinations [11], or a new flexible shield named Saba shielding [12] composed of bismuth in combination with other low atomic number metals

used to reduce the breast surface doses without any side effects on the image quality. However, the mentioned shields are not widely used in routine CT examinations due to the lack of accessibility. Herein, in the current work, we have assessed the impact of the common lead apron positioned in the chest regions to measure the breast surface dose as well as breast radiation-induced cancer and mortality risks during the head CT examinations. It should be noted that the apron used in our study is accessible in all CT centers easily.

Materials and Methods

Patients

Twenty-eight female patients with ages ranging from 23 to 74 years and a mean body mass index (BMI) of 25.2 ± 2.8 kg/m² referred to head CT examination for objective medical reasons were selected randomly for this study. The patients with breast surface infections or lesions were excluded.

The current study was approved by the Ethics Committee and National Research Ethics Board with registration number "IR.MUBABOL.REC.1399.484". Written informed consent was obtained from all participants, and the patients were informed that the study protocol was no invasive procedure.

CT scanning

A multi-detector CT scanner (16 slices, Siemens Healthcare GmbH, Erlangen, Germany) was used to acquire the head images. Notably, the patients were positioned supine, and their arms were lying beside their bodies. In a conventional standard head CT protocol, all scans were performed without any contrast agents. Table 1 represents the related parameters for the head CT scanning.

Table 1. CT scan parameters used for brain examination averaged over all participants

Parameter	Value
Tube voltage (kVp)	110
Effective mAs	150
Rotation time (s)	0.6
Pitch	0.95
CTDIvol (mGy)	24.33 ± 1.6
DLP (mGy.cm)	531.81 ± 30
Total scan time (s)	7.35 ± 1.58
Slice thickness (mm)	6
Slice number	30 ± 1
Gantry tilt	-1.5 ± 2.8 (-5 to +4)

Thermoluminescent dosimeter (TLD)

Breast surface doses were estimated using thermoluminescent dosimeter (TLD-100) chips. TLD chips are made of LiF, Mg, and Ti (thickness: 0.9 mm, size: 3×3 mm²) and produced by Harshaw Company (Thermo Electron Corporation, Reading, UK). The

TLDs were annealed in a TLD annealing furnace (1 h at 400°C and 2 h at 100°C), and they were pre-heated at 100°C for 20 minutes prior to the readout.

The TLD calibration processes were carried out based on Groves et al.'s study [13]. Briefly, to increase the reproducibility, the element correction coefficient (ECC) values were obtained for the TLDs. A calibrated Barracuda dosimeter (RTI Electronics, Sweden) was utilized for the confirmation of the dose measurement. To obtain ECCs, the TLDs were irradiated three times at the center of the CT scanner. Then, the mean readout values of the TLDs were calculated using the following equation:

$$ECC_i = TLD_i / TLD_{\text{mean}} \quad (1)$$

In addition, for obtaining the calibration factor (CF), the TLDs, with the ECC close to 1, were exposed three times to various selected doses, and the average readouts were calculated. After that, a figure was plotted based on the dose (mGy) versus TLD reading (nC), and the CF was obtained using the slope of the curve. Notably, a pair of TLD chips were located more than 3 meters far from the source of radiation (CT room) to measure the background dose. In the end, the surface dose was estimated using multiplying the mean values of the TLD readouts, ECC, and CF.

Dose measurement

Chest regions were covered with two folded lead aprons (0.5 mm thicknesses) during the head CT examination. For each patient, 6 TLDs were used to measure the dose of scatter radiation at the breast surface (one breast for each participant). Three TLDs were attached to the top surface of the apron, and three others, at the same location, were positioned under the apron (Figure 1; a and b).

The above dosimeters represent the received dose of the scattered and leakage radiations from the CT scanner. The TLD dosimeters positioned under the apron present the dose of scattered radiations from the patient's body.

Cancer risk estimation

The breasts' mean doses obtained from TLD measurements were used for cancer risk estimation based on the Biological Effects of Ionizing Radiation (BEIR-VII) report preferred model. This model uses a no-threshold linear relation as the most suitable relationship between low doses of ionizing radiation and the radiation-induced cancer and cancer mortality risks (up to age 90). This report considers various parameters, including cancer type, age at exposure, gender, and time elapsed after exposure, as the moderating factors [14]. Furthermore, a linear-quadratic model was utilized to estimate the risk of leukemia in this model; however, we only evaluated the radiation-induced breast cancer risks. The report uses a multi-risk index estimation model for community-specific risk frequencies [14].

Figure 1. The location of the TLD dosimeters, under the lead apron (a) and over the lead apron (b).

A combination of progressive and incremental models has been used to estimate the cancer risk based on age at radiation time (between progressive and incremental models). The committee has finally presented the life-attributed risks (LARs) for radiation-induced cancer and mortality risks at various cancers sites, ages and gender. The LAR is an estimate of the probability of developing premature cancer from radiation exposure over the life of the subject. These values present the additional risk of different cancers and the total risk of all cancers for ages (at the time of exposure) ranging from 0 to 80 years in both sexes for a dose of 0.1 Gy per 100,000 individuals [14]. Since all CT scans in the current study belonged to adult patients, we evaluated cancer incidence and mortality risk in women aged 20 to 80 years (10-year step) to prepare the related data of head CT imaging. To find the breast cancer risk for patients at various ages, we only multiplied the breast doses with breast cancer LAR values. Based on the preferred method reported in the BEIR-VII model, the organ mean doses were used for cancer risk estimation. TLD measurements on the skin were attributed to an appropriate depth, d , below the skin. The $H_p(d)$ obtained from the TLD reading after the calibration procedure represents the absorbed dose from external exposure in the depth of d . We used the reported conversion coefficients from air-kerma to $H_p(7\text{ mm})$. This dose was considered the organ (breast) absorbed dose and was used for breast cancer risk estimation.

Statistical analysis

The normality of the data was assessed by Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) statistical test. A Paired sample T-test was used to compare the dose received over and under the lead shielding, with the significance level at $P < 0.05$. All tests were performed in SPSS software, version 16 (IBM, USA)

Results

All studied patients had good compliance, and none exhibited pain during the experimental shield work. The

mean \pm standard deviation of the breast surface doses was 0.18 ± 0.06 and 0.49 ± 0.13 mGy, respectively, under and over the lead apron shield during the head CT scanning. The mean dose values were reduced significantly in the presence (over) of the apron (P -value < 0.001), with a percentage of 63.

Lifetime attributed breast cancer incidence and mortality risks due to the head CT scan in female patients under and over the lead aprons at different ages of exposure are presented in Figures 2 and 3, respectively. The results of the pair sample T-test demonstrated that the lifetime attributed breast cancer incidence and mortality risks had significant differences between over and under the lead apron in all ages of exposure ($P < 0.003$). Although all the cancer risks for both groups are very low, using a lead apron could decrease breast cancer incidence ($[1.24 \pm 0.32] \times 10^{-3}$ % over the apron vs. $[0.46 \pm 0.15] \times 10^{-3}$ % under the apron) and mortality risk ($[0.30 \pm 0.08] \times 10^{-3}$ % over the apron vs. $[0.11 \pm 0.04] \times 10^{-3}$ % under the apron) about 63% in all patients.

Figure 2. Mean \pm standard deviation values of lifetime attributed breast cancer incidence risks due to the head CT scan in the female patients over and under the lead aprons at different ages of exposures. Risk values are presented as incidence probability per 100,000 individuals.

Figure 3. Mean±standard deviation values of lifetime attributed breast cancer mortality risks due to the head CT scan in the female patients over and under the lead aprons at different ages of exposures. Risk values are presented as incidence probability per 100,000 individuals.

Discussion

Previous studies declared that scattered radiation from the organs could be reached the radiosensitive organs. For example, ovaries are inevitably exposed to significant scatter doses during abdominal CT scans, and the thyroid is exposed to head and neck CT examinations [15,16]. Additionally, several studies have reported that the testis can receive the dose from chest CT scans [17-20].

Based on the National Radiological Protection Board (NRPB) recommendation, there is no such thing as a “harmless radiation dose” [21]; therefore, every method which can reduce the dose should be carried out, besides keeping the image quality compared to the primary beam. In this regard, in the present work, breast surface doses during the head CT examinations were estimated when the lead apron (commonly accessible in the radiology centers) was used. Additionally, breast radiation-induced cancer incidence and mortality risks were estimated.

TLDs were used for the dose measurements because of their small size, and the expected doses were sufficiently high to give accurate readings. In addition, a typical lead apron as an accessible tool was used in a way that its impact was reported when it was utilized for the testis regions during the chest examination [19].

In the current study, two TLD groups for measuring the dose values (dose received over and under the lead apron) were positioned from one breast side of each patient to calculate the effect of apron shielding for the same breast. It must be mentioned that the leakage radiations can be different in the spatial positions of the right and left breasts; therefore, comparing each breast with itself can be an appropriate method to avoid this problem.

In line with the current study, a few studies investigated the breast surface dose during the head examination because scattering radiation generated in the patient's head and the gantry reaches superficial organs, particularly breasts [22]. In a study by Beaconsfield et al. [23], they assessed the effectiveness of a dental-style protective bib in reducing the dose to the radiosensitive organs. In this regard, the radiation doses over the breast (phantom model) were measured with a flat ionization chamber in 110 patients undergoing routine head CT scans. The results were compared with the shielded breast, and the average reduction of 76% in breast dose was obtained. In another study by Zalokar and Mekiš [9], they used a lead shield with 0.5 mm equivalent density for breast during head CT examination on an anthropomorphic phantom. They reported that the lead shield caused a significant dose reduction in both helical and axial CT protocols. In a way that this reduction was 96% in Hospital A and 82% in Hospital B for helical protocol, and 95% in Hospital A and 86% in Hospital B for axial protocol. Brnić et al. [22] found a 57 % dose reduction of the breast during the use of a lead apron (0.35-mm-equivalent lead density) in head conventional CT scanning. The radiation doses were measured by the TLDs located at the surface of the left unshielded breast, and the right breast was covered by a lead apron, in which the TLDs were positioned over the apron. Finally, the amount of scatter radiation was measured for the two breast sides, and the values were compared.

Furthermore, the same method of Brnić et al. was performed in a patient study by Chung et al. [24], and the breast surface dose reduction was obtained at 5.33, 17, 4.26, 5.36, and 2.16%, respectively, during the CT examinations of head, abdomen, lumbar, neck, and dynamic liver. The breast surface dose reduction was obtained at 63% during the head CT scan in our study. Also, there are several studies investigating the percentage of the dose reduction in the breast region during chest examinations using a bismuth shield [11, 25-29]. Figure 4 depicts a summary of the breast (surface) dose reduction in some other related studies performed on the phantom/patient during the head/chest examinations, compared with the present study. Although both patient and phantom studies would measure the breast scattered dose, in vivo (patient) measurement is a real clinical circumstance of patient positioning as well as variations of body geometry, which influence shielding possibilities. In general, the difference in the dose reduction may be attributed to the use of different shielding, various types of dosimeters, study models (phantom or patient), lead apron thicknesses, CT scan modalities (conventional or spiral), and different methods.

Figure 4. The dose reduction (%) in the breast during the head and chest CT examinations using lead and bismuth shielding in some studies. Patient: Patient study, Phantom: Phantom study, and Bi: bismuth. Bismuth shielding was used during the chest CT examinations, and lead apron was used during the head CT examinations.

Exposure to ionizing radiation is of concern because evidence has expressed that exposure to low-level ionizing radiation at doses utilized in medical imaging develops cancer [30]. Additionally, it has been reported that since the increasing use of CT scans and high exposure per examination, many cases of cancer result directly from CT [30]. Studies also reported that if head CT examinations are performed several times in the lifetime of a patient, the dose to the breasts (especially in younger women with glandular breasts) might accumulate to a significant level [22]. In this regard, breast shielding may be biologically significant in reducing breast radiation-induced cancer incidence and mortality risks during head scans. We obtained these findings when the lead apron was used for breasts during head CT. It is suggested that further study (based on our purpose) should be carried out on children group since their organs are more sensitive than adults.

Conclusion

As the results demonstrated, the common lead apron, a cost-effective tool that could be found easily in every center, reduced breast surface doses significantly (2.3 times) when used during the head MDCT scans in a patient study. Notably, breast radiation-induced cancer incidence and mortality risks were decreased remarkably in the presence (over) of the lead apron. Therefore, this lead apron shield would be recommended in the breast regions during routine head CT examinations.

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References

1. Abedi R, Ghaemian N, Monfared AS, Kiapour M, Abedi-Firouzjah R, Niksirat F, Agbele AT, Gorji KE. Can leaded glasses protect the eye lens in patients undergoing neck computed tomography?. *Journal of Clinical and Translational Research*. 2021 Aug 8;7(4):428.
2. Popovtzer R, Agrawal A, Kotov NA, Popovtzer A, Balter J, Carey TE, Kopelman R. Targeted gold nanoparticles enable molecular CT imaging of cancer. *Nano letters*. 2008 Dec 10;8(12):4593-6.
3. Davoudi M, Khoramian D, Abedi-Firouzjah R, Ataei G. Strategy of computed tomography image optimisation in cervical vertebrae and neck soft tissue in emergency patients. *Radiation protection dosimetry*. 2019 Dec 31;187(1):98-102.
4. Khoramian D, Sistani S, Firouzjah RA. Assessment and comparison of radiation dose and image quality in multi-detector CT scanners in non-contrast head and neck examinations. *Polish Journal of Radiology*. 2019 Jan 23;84:61-7.
5. Protection R. ICRP publication 103. *Ann ICRP*. 2007;37(2.4):2.
6. Oertel M, Kelly DF, McArthur D, Boscardin WJ, Glenn TC, Lee JH, Gravori T, Obukhov D, McBride DQ, Martin NA. Progressive hemorrhage after head trauma: predictors and consequences of the evolving injury. *Journal of neurosurgery*. 2002 Jan 1;96(1):109-16.
7. Brown CV, Weng J, Oh D, Salim A, Kasotakis G, Demetriades D, Velmahos GC, Rhee P. Does routine serial computed tomography of the head influence management of traumatic brain injury? A prospective evaluation. *Journal of Trauma and Acute Care Surgery*. 2004 Nov 1;57(5):939-43.
8. Phan CM, Yoo AJ, Hirsch JA, Nogueira RG, Gupta R. Differentiation of hemorrhage from iodinated contrast in different intracranial compartments using dual-energy head CT. *American journal of neuroradiology*. 2012 Jun 1;33(6):1088-94.
9. Zalokar N, Mekiš N. A phantom study showing the importance of breast shielding during head CT.

- Radiation Protection Dosimetry. 2020 Mar;188(4):464-9.
10. Mehnati P, Ghavami M, Heidari H. Reducing radiation doses in female breast and lung during CT examinations of thorax: A new technique in two scanners. *Journal of biomedical physics & engineering*. 2017 Sep;7(3):217.
 11. Colombo P, Pedroli G, Nicoloso M, Re S, Valvassori L, Vanzulli A. Evaluation of the efficacy of a bismuth shield during CT examinations. *La Radiologia Medica*. 2004 Nov 1;108(5-6):560-8.
 12. Saba V, Keshkar M. Targeted radiation energy modulation using Saba shielding reduces breast dose without degrading image quality during thoracic CT examinations. *Physica Medica*. 2019 Sep 1;65:238-46.
 13. Groves AM, Owen KE, Courtney HM, Yates SJ, Goldstone KE, Blake GM, Dixon AK. 16-detector multislice CT: dosimetry estimation by TLD measurement compared with Monte Carlo simulation. *The British journal of radiology*. 2004 Aug;77(920):662-5.
 14. National Research Council. Health risks from exposure to low levels of ionizing radiation: BEIR VII phase 2.
 15. Mazonakis M, Tzedakis A, Damilakis J, Gourtsoyiannis N. Thyroid dose from common head and neck CT examinations in children: is there an excess risk for thyroid cancer induction?. *European radiology*. 2007 May;17(5):1352-7.
 16. Su YP, Niu HW, Chen JB, Fu YH, Xiao GB, Sun QF. Radiation dose in the thyroid and the thyroid cancer risk attributable to CT scans for pediatric patients in one general hospital of China. *International journal of environmental research and public health*. 2014 Mar;11(3):2793-803.
 17. Grobe H, Sommer M, Koch A, Hietschold V, Henniger J, Abolmaali N. Dose reduction in computed tomography: the effect of eye and testicle shielding on radiation dose measured in patients with beryllium oxide-based optically stimulated luminescence dosimetry. *European radiology*. 2009 May;19(5):1156-60.
 18. Iball GR, Brettle DS. Organ and effective dose reduction in adult chest CT using abdominal lead shielding. *The British Journal of Radiology*. 2011 Nov;84(1007):1020-6.
 19. Kiapour M, Gorji KE, Mehraeen R, Ghaemian N, Sustani FN, Abedi-Firouzjah R, Monfared AS. Can Common Lead Apron in Testes Region Cause Radiation Dose Reduction during Chest CT Scan? A Patient Study. *Journal of Biomedical Physics & Engineering*. 2021 Aug;11(4):497.
 20. Sancaktutar AA, Bozkurt Y, Önder H, Söylemez H, Atar M, Penbegül N, Ziypak T, Tekbaş G, Tepeler A. A new practical model of testes shield: the effectiveness during abdominopelvic computed tomography. *Journal of andrology*. 2012 Sep 10;33(5):984-9.
 21. Hart D, Hillier MC, Wall BF. Doses to patients from medical X-ray examinations in the UK. 2000 review.
 22. Brnić Z, Vekić B, Hebrang A, Anić P. Efficacy of breast shielding during CT of the head. *European radiology*. 2003 Nov;13(11):2436-40.
 23. Beaconsfield T, Nicholson R, Thornton A, Al-Kutoubi A. Would thyroid and breast shielding be beneficial in CT of the head?. *European radiology*. 1998 May;8(4):664-7.
 24. Chung JJ, Cho ES, Kang SM, Yu JS, Kim DJ, Kim JH. Usefulness of a lead shielding device for reducing the radiation dose to tissues outside the primary beams during CT. *La radiologia medica*. 2014 Dec;119(12):951-7.
 25. Mehnati P, Malekzadeh R, Sooteh MY. Use of bismuth shield for protection of superficial radiosensitive organs in patients undergoing computed tomography: a literature review and meta-analysis. *Radiological Physics and Technology*. 2019 Mar;12(1):6-25.
 26. Yilmaz MH, Albayram S, Yasar D, Özer H, Adaletli I, Selçuk D, Akman C, Altug A. Female breast radiation exposure during thorax multidetector computed tomography and the effectiveness of bismuth breast shield to reduce breast radiation dose. *Journal of computer assisted tomography*. 2007 Jan 1;31(1):138-42.
 27. Hohl C, Wildberger JE, Süß C, Thomas C, Mühlenbruch G, Schmidt T, Honnef D, Günther RW, Mahnken AH. Radiation dose reduction to breast and thyroid during MDCT: effectiveness of an in-plane bismuth shield. *Acta Radiologica*. 2006 Jan 1;47(6):562-7.
 28. Alonso TC, Mourão AP, Santana PC, da Silva TA. Assessment of breast absorbed doses during thoracic computed tomography scan to evaluate the effectiveness of bismuth shielding. *Applied Radiation and Isotopes*. 2016 Nov 1;117:55-7.
 29. Ko CH, Lee SP, Hsieh YC, Lee YH, Yao MM, Chan WP. Bismuth breast-shield use in chest computed tomography for efficient dose reduction and sufficient image quality. *Medicine*. 2021 Jun 6;100(25).
 30. Smith-Bindman R, Lipson J, Marcus R, Kim KP, Mahesh M, Gould R, De González AB, Miglioretti DL. Radiation dose associated with common computed tomography examinations and the associated lifetime attributable risk of cancer. *Archives of internal medicine*. 2009 Dec 14;169(22):2078-86.